

Navigating the Nexus: How Transformational Leadership and Cultural Diversity Influence Employee Creative Behaviour through Employee Information Elaboration

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ABSTRACT: This study examines the interacting effects of transformational leadership and cultural diversity on enhancing employee creative behaviours in the workplace, with a focus on the mediating role of employee information elaboration. Utilizing the social information processing theory as the theoretical framework, the research clarifies how transformational leadership and cultural diversity influence employee creative behaviour through the cultured processing of diverse informational inputs. The methodology implements on a quantitative method, engaging a stratified random sample of 260 employees from various manufacturing organizations. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire, consist of the transformational leadership and cultural diversity, the elaboration of information about and employee creative behaviour. AMOS and SPSS software were used in the analysis; SEM was adopted to determine the causal relationships between the constructs. Research demonstrates that transformational cross cultural leadership has a positive relation with employee information elaboration and employee creative behaviour, where employee information elaboration acts as a mediator in these processes. Particularly, the transformational leadership and cultural diversity were unprotected to have a significant impact on employee creativity by encouraging their information elaboration, which supports the proposed hypotheses that improved employee information processing boosts manufacturing employees' creativity. Therefore, the outcomes of these findings are as follows. In terms of policy recommendations, the study encourages manufacturing managers to promote diversity and bring out transformational leadership to the manufacturing facility to improve for innovation and creativity. Theoretically, it improves social information processing theory by explaining how employee information elaboration is a mediator of the identified relationship between cultural diversity and employee creativity on the individual level. This study improves leadership and diversity management allowance, offering a novel approach to using strategic information elaboration to raise employee creativity and providing practical strategies for directing diverse, competitive markets.

Keywords: Cultural Diversity, Employee Creative Behaviour, Employee Information Elaboration, Transformational Leadership, Social Information Processing Theory

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1. Introduction

In today's globalized business environment, the complication and importance of managing a diverse workforce have never been more noticeable. As globalization advances and brings down the barriers of national boundaries in the business world, it becomes inevitable to address the issues of diversity in workforce. The globalization of business has necessitated the need to have a proper approach towards the culturally diverse employees in order to improve on the innovation as well as competitiveness. Organizations all over the world are facing the question of how to adequately address the issue of cultural diversity (CD) and leadership. The understanding of the concepts of transformational leadership (TL) and cultural diversity is not confined to the industries mentioned above but is paramount in the general global business world given the current call for organizations to create environments that encourage innovation and creativity. In addressing this global issue, this study focuses on the role of TL and CD in improving the employee creative behavior (ECB) by facilitating the process of information elaboration among culturally diverse teams in the manufacturing sector. This has become important as companies across the globe look at ways to compete effectively in various and growing markets.

According to Tamunomiebi and John-Eke (2020), emphasize that diversity is a crucial source of creativity, serving as a foundation for competitive advantage. Culture, as defined by Hofstede (1980) is the collection of features distinguishing one group from another, including meanings, symbols, values, norms, and beliefs recognized by a community (H. Schwartz, 2006, Velarde et al., 2022). However, diversity can also lead to misunderstandings, doubts, and conflicts in the workplace, potentially causing absenteeism, diminished work quality, reduced morale, and a loss of competitive edge (Tamunomiebi and John-Eke, 2020). Additionally, companies with culturally diverse workforces may need to invest in incorporating these diverse elements to enhance employee creativity (Dale-Olsen and Finseraas, 2020). Cobanoglu (2021) highlights the importance of acknowledging individual differences and needs in defining TL, with leaders needing to understand and motivate employees based on these personal attributes (Demir, 2021).

Effective diversity management ensures that all employees are provided equal opportunities and are respected for their unique characteristics (Belloda and Oğuzhan, 2017, Çelik, 2019). This study adopts the information-exchange perspective to explore how employee cultural diversity impacts employee creativity (Li et al., 2017). According to this perspective, sharing knowledge is vital for fostering employee creativity (Gong et al., 2013). Through employee information elaborations, employee can access a broader array of resources, sparking the generation of creative solutions to complex challenges (Grant and Ashford, 2008). Our focus on EIE examines how the process of information elaboration

allows for the emergence of valuable and novel ideas within the workplace, enhancing creativity among employees (Li et al., 2017).

Research in transformational leadership and cultural diversity continues to change, but there remains a different gap in their collective evaluation, particularly in enhancing creative behaviours through information elaboration in manufacturing settings. Studies on CD like those by (Li et al., 2017, Wang et al., 2019) highlight its positive effects on employee creativity, sharing information in employee while recent insights into cultural diversity's benefits on business performance are detailed by (Khumalo and Zondo, 2021). Particularly, research by Braun et al. (2013) and Abouraia and Othman (2017) explore the association among TL and Cultural Intelligence but short of exploring their interactive effects on EIE and ECB. This inaccuracy is significant, given the potential for TL and CD to optimize the benefits of ECB through EIE, a connection suggested but not empirically tested in studies. Our research aims to fill this crucial gap by empirically testing how TL and CD can control to promote enhanced EIE and thus increase ECB.

The vital for this study arises from a critical examination of current practices and gaps within the manufacturing sector, particularly in attaching the full potential of TL and CD. As the sector continues to globalize, the diversity within workforce demographics intensifies, presenting both challenges and opportunities for creativity and productivity. Despite substantial studies on the organizational outcomes of TL and CD, there is still a lack of appropriate literature on the interaction between the two factors regarding their impact on the EIE and the encouragement of creativity. This research aims to address this important knowledge gap by examining TL as a form of leadership that can optimally manage CD, enhance information processing, as well as creativity among the employees.

The contribution of this research is dual: firstly, it presents the new empirical model linking TL and CD as a tool to boost creative performance in the manufacturing organizations; secondly, it gives the practical guidelines for the manufacturing managers on how to address CD as key to creativity and competitive advantage. Thus, this research not only advances the field's scholarship but also provides practitioners with leverage to enhance their business functionality and responsiveness in a growingly competitive international environment.

2. Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

Social Information Processing Theory (SIP), expressed by Salancik and Pfeffer (1978), suggests that individuals' attitudes and behaviours in the workplace are shaped not solely by objective job characteristics but significantly by social indications and the informational context provided by others in the environment. Within organizational frameworks, the combination of TL and CD has further been examined as necessary for cultivating innovation (Ince, 2023). Nevertheless, there are still some research gaps referring to the interplay of these factors and how they affect ECB and with the role of information elaboration as a mediator in this process (Jiang et al., 2023). This deficiency is at odds with the fact that many organizations claim to work with diverse people in terms of

gender, race, or sexual orientation(Howard, 2023); however, misunderstanding of how these interactions take place may prevent organizations from achieving their full creative potential and stall, subsequently losing competitiveness in global markets. Earlier research has found TL and CD as independent entities and looked at how they influence multiple organizational outcomes independently (Muharam, 2023, Pham et al., 2023, Tlili et al., 2023, Maqsoom et al., 2023). However, no prior work examines the combined impacts of these variables and how exactly they interdepend to generate the optimum impacts on ECB. This research seeks to address this gap by examining the mediating role of EIE on the relationships between TL, CD, and creativity in organizations, which would give a clear insight on how these factors could be utilized effectively for the enhancement of employee creativity.

Likewise, CD introduces a scope of perspectives and experiences into the organizational environment, further enriching the social information context. When individuals from varied cultural backgrounds interact, it expands the base of ideas, opinions, and insights available within employees or organizations. This diversity just not only develops the knowledgeable content but also confuses the information treating directions, hypothetically leading to more creativity and innovation consequences as employees manufacture diverse perspectives. EIE acts as a mediating variable that interprets the partial social information formed by both TL and CD into creative outputs. According to SIP theory, the way information is elaborated upon and utilized in decision-making and problem-solving processes critically determines the creative capabilities of employees. Thus, understanding the mediating role of EIE is essential for the benefits of leadership and diversity in promoting creativity within organizations.

The Impact of Cultural Diversity on Employee Creative Behaviour

Diversity includes a range of unique attributes that differentiate among individuals from one another, including but not limited to gender, race, ethnicity, age, education, and disability (Klarsfeld et al., 2012, Orsini and Magnier-Watanabe, 2023). The transformative effect of such diversity in the workplace has been extensively documented, underscoring its ability to enhance organizational outcomes. Particularly, Huselid (1995) demonstrated how human resource management practices personalized to assorted workforces significantly influence both employee productivity and corporate financial performance. Further substantiating this, Hajro et al. (2017) discovered that the incorporation of diverse perspectives particularly improves work processes.

In the scope of manufacturing, where the critical issue is innovation, there can be no overestimation of CD. Technologically, the sector has developed at a very fast bound and as such, there is need for a workforce that not only diverse but also needs to be an artistic one. In this case, diversity also serves as a tool for promoting improvement in concern to idea generation and business process effectiveness. Hajro et al. (2017) stated that diversity at workplace translates to higher profitability of companies and business organizations while maintaining that diversity goes away from these issue of equality to affect business outcomes.

However, the prospective of diverse opportunities for capability, one must look beyond simple acknowledgement of the idea. Clearly, as Davis et al. (2016) highlighted,

diversity in the workers leads to the development of a number of diverse concerns, which if not well allocated with may be problematic (Orsini and Magnier-Watanabe, 2023). The modern demand for manufacturing work, which inclines to decrease the degree of the structural differentiation of activities and increase the importance of the knowledge factor as a factor of labor productivity requires creativity-oriented labor (Pitta, 2009, Moghimi and Subramaniam, 2013). According to Orsini and Magnier-Watanabe (2023), “creativity can be described as the generation of ideas which are new and useful in solving organizational challenges as well as which matches organizational vision and strategies.” In this context, manufacturing organizations that influence the varied backgrounds of their workforce effectively create an environment where creative solutions succeed. The interaction between varied cultural perspectives and the dynamic requirements of manufacturing roles enhances the sector's ability to innovate and adapt in an increasingly competitive market.

According to George and Zhou (2001), ECB, which includes the generation of novel and useful ideas, can significantly raise creativity. This is especially relevant in manufacturing where the complication of production processes and customer interactions demand constant creativity. The interaction between ECB and CD not only helps to develop the participants' working environments but also contributes to the sector's advancement as fresh ideas incentive shifts that are vital for its enhancement and success (Moghimi and Subramaniam, 2013). It must be noted that incorporation of CD and ECB is not only useful but critical for sustained growth and diffusion of new technologies in manufacturing. These dynamics of CD interaction with ECB impart the vital function of participating different perspectives for the frequent development and competitive advantage in the manufacturing sector and presenting the basis for the next hypothesis:

H1: Cultural diversity is significantly positively influences the employee creative behaviour.

The Role of Transformational Leadership in Promoting Employee Creative Behaviour

In the dynamic dominion of manufacturing, where creativity and innovation is critical for competitive advantage, TL appears as an essential strength in enhancing ECB. This leadership style, comprehensively studied across various academic disciplines, significantly impacts crucial organizational outcomes, including performance, engagement, and innovative output (Bass and Avolio, 1994, Antonakis, 2001, Ibrahim, 2023). TL, known for their idealistic approach, inspire and motivate employees other than the standard expectations by fostering an environment conducive to creativity and innovation (Ibrahim, 2023). These leaders are proficient to recognizing and development of the unique talents of each employee, thereby encouraging them to explore new ideas and creative solutions. In manufacturing, where project management and continuous process improvements are vital, TL has proven especially effective (Ibrahim, 2023, Turner and Müller, 2005). The interaction between TL and ECB is particularly apparent in the front lines of manufacturing. Here, leaders who embrace transformational tactics enable their workforce to exceed ordinary performance levels, thus facilitating the generation of creative ideas and solutions. Researches have shown that concept generating front line employees guided by transformational leaders are able to produce significantly more unique and valuable

outcomes compared to their complements in transactional environments (George and Zhou, 2001).

Moreover, introducing and practicing TL has an impact on such organizational culture factors as trust, which leads to the support of group cohesiveness and individual motivation (Jung and Sosik, 2002, Greimel et al., 2023). This type of culture enables the employees to be comfortable and open and creative and take risk, which are part of creativity in manufacturing industries. TL are significantly more effective in face-to-face communication, thus enabling them to determine the organisational climate and positively encourage employees creativity (Greimel et al., 2023). Additionally, the link between TL, motivation, and meaningful work further underscores the critical role of such leaders in facilitating ECB. Employees are more likely to engage in creative activities when they find their work meaningful and are supported by leaders who encourage their professional growth and value their contributions (Bailey et al., 2019). The understanding that TL significantly impact organizational dynamics and ECB, it is hypothesized that:

H2: Transformational leadership is significantly positively influences the employee creative behaviour.

Enhancing Employee Information Elaboration through Transformational Leadership

The theoretical framework of SIP Theory, to establish how TL improves EIE by promoting collaboration and work motivation. TL, initially described by Burns (2012), combines the results of the leaders' and followers' elevation of each other's stature. This leadership style is very efficient where the leaders are physically present with the subordinates and in other face-to-face communication platforms because it enhances the motivation of employees (Givens, 2008). Research by Bailey et al. (2018) also faces that TL is positively linked with meaningful work and employees' motivation which is critical components for creativity and efficiency in employees. Further, the study of transformational leaders uncovered that they experience higher levels of, and empowering employees, cohesiveness, and apparent efficiency associated to the transactional leaders (Jung and Sosik, 2002, Greimel et al., 2023). However, the implementation of TL has been most pointed in the manufacturing industry. It has also been explained by Mittal and Dhar (2016) how TL leads to green creativity through the provision of wisdom, direction, and support to employees to be environmental constructive; at the same time, TL helps the growth of the employees (Ilyas et al., 2024a). This kind of leadership also increases the organizational performance and organizational commitment, trust, and environmental performance standards (Mittal and Dhar, 2016). Additional to its effectiveness, TL affects the improvement of learning environment in which employees operate, exploring ways to enhance their performance and the organizations' talent management as evidenced by Zhu et al. (2005) and Ilyas et al. (2024c) respectively. Such benefits are vital in stratified environments which demand creativity and flexibility as their main strategies.

Regarding EIE, transformational leaders improve this process because they create conditions that actively promote successful combination of ideas. In this regard, the position of EIE is quite crucial. Employees, with high EIE, are more effective in the holistic information processing, which is due to the fact that they are more able to interpret different

range of emotions and reasoning belonging to others (Wang, 2015, Canary and Cupach, 1988). Wang (2015) further explains that EIE raises a better interaction in the groups, allowing employees to develop a constructive improvement of each other's inputs. These mechanisms collectively improve EIE by fostering an environment where complex ideas are more easily understood and integrated, enhancing the innovative capacity of employees. Thus, the interplay between TL and EIE presents a dynamic framework within which teams can operate more effectively and creatively. In light of these discussions, the hypothesis is proposed:

H3: Transformational leadership is significantly Influences the employee information elaboration.

Cultural Diversity and Its Influence on Employee Information Elaboration

Grounded in the framework of SIP theory, the role of CD in improving EIE presents that social aspect of information processing, such as the cultural difference of the employees influence information processing in organizations as forecast by SIPT. This theory asserts that when there is variation in the information that is processed, there is improved decision making and creativity which are essential in organizations hence supporting the influences (Salancik and Pfeffer, 1978). EIE, fundamentally a cognitive demanding process, necessitates employees to utilize effort in assimilating and integrating diverse perspectives. This synthesis of varied viewpoints contributes significantly to the generation of new knowledge in the employees (Wang, 2015, Keltner and Haidt, 2001). The process of achieving effective EIE is not without some interferences. All these factors reveal that educational and functional differences present both possibilities for and limitations to group-level EIE (Harvey, 2015, Oad, 2020). Effective EIE demands that all employees engage compassionately with diverse perspectives and collaboratively integrate these insights (Homan et al., 2007, Oad, 2020).

The incorporation of multiple views can be easy task. Members of a group may have to understanding these differences that require creativity in the approaches to be used when trying to overcome and interface the various groups' perspectives (Harvey, 2015). Despite these challenges, information exchange enlarges the pool of knowledge that can be utilised to solve particular tasks while avoiding reinvention and, as a result, provides for a creative process combined with identification of problems, idea generation upon the existing body of data, and outcome assessment (Amabile, 2018). Thus, CD in employees may raise EIE by revealing the variety of views and knowledge, it has to be accomplished very carefully because it entails some obstacles integral to CD. Banono (2023) showed that CD at the workplace, especially in the aspects of ethnicity age and gender contributed to enhancement of possibilities of creativity within the employees , as confirmed by Aliyu and Abubakar (2024). The capability of employee in directing the above challenges determines the EIE process efficiency and, the innovative capacity of the organisation (Oad, 2020). These challenges pose significant risks. It is imperative for organizations to create experiences where culturally diverse employees can share their general perceptions and ideas with another because this will help properly connect the benefits of culturally diverse employees when it comes to manufacturing companies. This analysis underscores that the

relationship between CD and EIE is positively significant, leading to the following hypothesis:

H4: Cultural diversity is significantly positively influences the employee information elaboration.

Mediating Role of Employee Information Elaboration in Employee mediates the Creative Behaviour

The mediating role of EIE in ECB is pivotal, principally in contexts where deep-level diversity is current (Hobman et al., 2004). Information elaboration, which involves the detailed incorporation and examination of diverse ideas and information, is vital for making optimal decisions are stated that the development the generation of creative ideas (Harvey, 2015). This process demonstrates the significantly enhancement of group performance on complex or dynamic tasks that demand high levels of creativity (Hobman et al., 2004, Stasser and Titus, 1985). However, the benefits of EIE may not extend as strongly to more routine tasks, such as standard production work, where the complexity and demand for productivity and creativity are lower.

Moreover, EIE requires that different members compare and analyze implications that may grounded from one's information and different perspectives. Elaboration is an active process where none team members engage in a process of decision-making to assess the other's information for its accuracy and relevance in achieving the employees goal (Stasser and Titus, 1985). This process is pivotal in the evaluation and integration of multiple types of informative inputs within employee environment. Thus, the ECB is agreed as the planned generation of new and valuable ideas, methods or practices in the given context (Anderson et al., 2014, Jia et al., 2024). It should be understood that the framework of a particular organization, the idea can be unique, although globally it may not. Therefore, ECB should be considered as articulate feature located at the organizational level, which can differ at the individual, team, and task levels (Anderson et al., 2014). The concept of one continuous creativity is to have a big impact on competitiveness of manufacturing then the role of EIE in ECB should be understood. It also contributes towards the enhancement of the firm's competence for internal creativity and change initiation within the manufacturing discipline. EIE and ECB interaction is therefore an important component in the never-ending process of creativity, productivity and enhancement in the sector.

H5: Employee information elaboration is significantly positively influence employee creative behaviour.

Transformational leadership to Employee information elaboration mediates to employee creative behaviour

The connection between TL, EIE, and ECB in organizations forms the core of this investigation, particularly aimed at understanding its implications within the manufacturing sector. TL is popular for its positive impact on fostering organizational innovation by catalyzing employee creativity (Mumford et al., 2002). This leadership style enhances creativity by promoting an enriching and supportive work environment that encourages employees to engage in creative endeavors. Research underscores that transformational leaders, through behaviours such as idealized influence and individualized consideration,

provide a fertile ground for creative outputs (Bass and Avolio, 1994). Such leaders not only inspire trust and loyalty but also ensure focused communication with employees, facilitating a deeper understanding of their creative needs and potential barriers to creativity. This supportive interaction is crucial as it fosters an environment where employees feel valued and understood, thus more likely to engage proactively with creative challenges and continue despite obstacles (Tierney and Farmer, 2004).

Furthermore, creativity in the workplace, hypothesized as the generation of new ideas or products, is essential for driving creativity, growth, and societal development (Gilson, 2008, Chaubey et al., 2019). Employees are encouraged to critically evaluate inefficient methods and propose more effective solutions, behaviours revealing of personal initiative and creative behaviour. The mediating role of EIE in this dynamic becomes apparent as TL not only enhances the immediate creative capabilities of employees but also systematically improves the way information is processed and utilized for creativity. This mediation suggests that TL influences ECB directly and indirectly by enhancing the quality and depth of EIE. Thus, in manufacturing sectors where creativity is critical, leaders who adopt a transformational approach can significantly raise the creative output by enhancing the flow and integration of information across different employees' settings.

H6: Transformational leadership to Employee information elaboration significantly positively mediates the relationship between employee creative behaviour.

Cultural Diversity to Employee Information Elaboration Mediating Effect on Employee Creative Behaviour

In the dynamic of organizations, the role of CD in EIE through the mediating effect of ECB demonstrates a compelling area of study, principally within diverse work groups. When faced with critical decision-making, organizations commonly depend on the collective expertise of cross-functional employees, which are frequently more effective than individuals in reaching high-quality decisions due to the varied information and expertise they contribute (Argote et al., 2014, Choi, 2007). CD, as defined by Hofstede (2001), reflects the inherent values, beliefs, and identities that differentiate one group from another, effecting member behaviours within an organization. This diversity extends at multiple levels from employee to national culture and acts as a source of social identity (House et al., 2004, Homan et al., 2007). However, the incorporation of such varied cultural backgrounds can lead to both positive and negative outcomes. According to the SIP theory, the categorization-information elaboration model (CEM) hypothesizes that while CD can stimulate creativity and innovation, it can also introduce challenges such as cultural identity conflicts and intercultural communication difficulties, which can delay employee creativity (Van Knippenberg et al., 2020). The mediating role of ECB in the relationship between CD and EIE is crucial. ECB, which demands the generation of novel and useful ideas, acts as an association in this model. When diverse teams effectively manage the challenges posed by their cultural differences, they can influence their diverse perspectives to enhance the elaboration of information. This, in turn, fosters an environment encouraging to creative solutions, thereby potentially compensating the social costs associated with diversity.

H7: Cultural Diversity to Employee information elaboration significantly positively mediates the relationship of employee creative behaviour.

Figure: Conceptual Framework

3. Methodology

Population and Sampling

To analyze the factors of TL, CD, EIE and ECB, this study focuses the employees from different manufacturing industries. Participants for the study, and a stratified random sampling technique will be adopted with a view of ensuring that participants are selected from all the levels of management and functional areas in the sector being study. The number of participants is to be 260, which is statistically adequate while at the same time being practically possible. The process of identifying the right sample size for this study adopts guidelines as represented by Kline (2015) and Ilyas et al. (2024b), who recommended that the sample size for structural equation modeling (SEM) should adhere to the 10 times rule. This rule proposes that the sample size should be no less than 10 times the total number of questions included in the model, ensuring sufficient data for reliable analysis. This size is satisfactory for conducting complex statistical analyses, including path modeling to explore the interrelationships among the constructs.

Data Collection Method

The structured questionnaire developed from items reported in the previous literature. The questionnaire will be distributed in two formats to accommodate participant preferences and increase the response rate represent that 70% of the questionnaires will have an online mode of administration through online questionnaire, while 30% shall be the physical copied mode for use on firsthand by the participants who may not prefer the use of online questionnaires or may not have access to the internet. This distribution strategy means that most of the data can be gathered and analyzed very swiftly depending on the nature of the topic under research, at the same time targeting participants who may be shy

or frequently using technology. Therefore, the proposed design will allow for an expansion of potential participants and increased study validity.

Measures

Based on the theoretical descriptions, the questionnaire will include a total of 24 questions grouped under the TL, CD, EIE, and ECB scales. These measures were obtained from the validated scales that have been used in other research studies and have high reliability. In each item, the respondents will be asked to rate it using a Likert scale, thus making measurement on the constructs being investigated quantitative.

ECB, 4 specific items were used, initially derived by Farmer et al. (2003) and tested for the applicability in Chinese market. These items have been consistently used in prior studies like in the cross-sectional study by Zhang et al. (2023). Evaluations provided by direct supervisors who used phrases such as, "This employee actively seeks new ideas and solutions for problems" and "This employee is often the first to experiment with new methods or ideas."

TL was assessed using a six-item scale tailored for green product development projects. The scale, drawing on the conceptual foundations laid by Tichy and Devanna (1986) and further explored by Chen and Chang (2013), (Podsakoff et al., 1996), includes specific items such as "The leader of the green product development project provides a clear environmental vision for the project members to follow" and "The leader of the green product development project encourages the project members to achieve the environmental goals." This approach effectively evaluates how transformational leaders inspire and unify team efforts towards environmental objectives.

CD in the organization was measured using a 10-item scale designed by Raewf and Mahmood (2021). Items such as "The leadership at the organization encourages diversity" and "The organization provides an environment for the free and open expression of ideas, opinions, and beliefs" assess leadership support for diversity and the organizational climate for open communication, respectively. This scale effectively evaluates the organization's commitment to promoting and managing cultural diversity.

All EIE 4 items were obtained by developing a scale for this study because the current measures are not suitable for this field survey, according to Li et al. (2017) This scale consists of four items that capture the efforts made by employees who search for information concerning the tasks, think about received information, and apply it as well as the sources of information that they adopt, which may include fellow employees, own experiences, documents, the internet and others. The items developed offer understanding into the manner in which the employees act in handling info to attain at the most satisfactory solutions, "On the job, I make an effort to consider all task-related information to generate optimal solutions."

Data Analysis

The data collection was experienced a rigorous dual-phase analysis. We used AMOS for path modeling to explore the interrelationships among the constructs and SPSS for more detailed statistical analysis, ensuring data integrity and normality. This

comprehensive approach allowed us to meticulously dissect the mediating role of employee information elaboration in linking leadership and diversity to creative outputs.

4. Result & Findings

Result

Table 1: Respondent Demographics

		Frequency	Percentage %
Gender	Male	170	65.70
	Female	90	34.30
	Total	260	100.00
Education	14 Years	5	1.90
	16 Years	74	28.70
	M.Phil.	166	63.80
	PHD	15	5.60
	Total	260	100.00
Age	Less than 26	56	21.70
	26-35	55	20.90
	36-45	100	38.60
	46-55	44	16.90
	56 & above	5	1.90
	Total	260	100.00
Experience	Less than 1	55	21.20
	5-Jan	119	45.60
	10-Jun	50	19.30
	15-Nov	29	11.30
	16-20	5	1.90
	21 & above	2	0.80
	Total	260	100.00

Table 1 presents the demographics of 260 respondents. Gender distribution shows 65.7% males and 34.3% females. Most respondents (63.8%) hold a M.Phil. degree. The age group of 36-45 years is predominant at 38.6%. Regarding experience, 45.6% have 1-5 years, indicating a relatively young workforce. The data suggests a diverse mainly young and highly cultured sample.

Table 2: Discriminant validity

Items	ECB	TL	CD	EIE
ECB	0.850			
TL	0.465	0.849		
CD	0.330	0.390	0.877	
EIE	0.420	0.447	0.485	0.870

Table 2 displays the discriminant validity of the constructs in the study: ECB, TL, CD, and EIE. The transverse values, which represent the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE), show ECB at 0.850, TL at 0.849, CD at 0.877, and EIE at 0.870, all exceeding the threshold of 0.7, indicating strong construct validity. The off-diagonal values

represent the correlations between constructs, all of which are lower than the diagonal values, authorizing that each concept is different and provides good discriminant validity. This validates the model's construct reliability and the particularity of each variable.

Table 3: Factor Loading

Variables	Items	Loading Factor	Alpha	CR	AVE
Employee Creative Behaviour	ECB1	0.810	0.876	0.915	0.729
	ECB2	0.894			
	ECB3	0.913			
	ECB4	0.859			
Transformational Leadership	TL1	0.827	0.898	0.930	0.768
	TL2	0.836			
	TL3	0.833			
	TL4	0.895			
	TL5	0.852			
Employee Information Elaboration	EIE1	0.800	0.899	0.930	0.721
	EIE2	0.851			
	EIE3	0.901			
	EIE4	0.861			
Cultural Diversity	CD1	0.837	0.890	0.925	0.57
	CD2	0.911			
	CD3	0.881			
	CD4	0.870			
	CD5	0.861			
	CD6	0.874			
	CD7	0.856			
	CD8	0.910			
	CD9	0.902			

Table 3 showcases the factor loadings, Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR), and AVE for each construct within the study: ECB, TL, EIE, and CD. Each construct demonstrates high internal consistency as evidenced by Alphas and CR values all above the acceptable threshold of 0.7, indicating robust reliability. ECB shows strong loadings ranging from 0.810 to 0.913 and an AVE of 0.729, reflecting good convergent validity. TL, after dropping one item, still presents strong loadings between 0.827 and 0.895 with a high AVE of 0.768. EIE items also display high loadings (0.800 to 0.901) and a suitable AVE of 0.721. CD, despite the removal of an item, exhibits loadings from 0.837 to 0.911 but has a slightly lower AVE of 0.57, which might suggest re-evaluating some items for better construct representation. The data confirms that each construct is well-defined and represents distinct aspects as hypothesized in the study.

Table 4: Structural Equation Modeling

No	Hypotheses	Mean	Standard Deviation	T-value	P-value	Result
H1	CD → ECB	0.035	0.034	8.645	0.000	Supported
H2	TL → ECB	0.032	0.030	11.340	0.000	Supported

H3	TL → EIE	0.901	0.019	47.183	0.000	Supported
H4	CD → EIE	0.036	0.013	2.726	0.007	Supported
H5	EIE → ECB	0.012	0.018	2.163	0.031	Supported
Indirect Effect						
H6	TL → EIE → ECB	0.031	0.030	2.157	0.021	Supported
H7	CD → EIE → ECB	0.034	0.025	2.172	0.020	Supported

Table 4 details the results from the Structural Equation Modeling, assessing the relationships between CD, TL, EIE, and ECB. The direct effect of CD on ECB (Hypothesis 1) is supported with a mean effect of 0.035, standard deviation of 0.034, a t-value of 8.645, and a significant p-value of 0.000. Similarly, the impact of TL on ECB (Hypothesis 2) shows a mean of 0.032, standard deviation of 0.030, t-value of 11.340, and a significant p-value of 0.000, indicating strong support.

The effect of TL on EIE (Hypothesis 3) is particularly strong, with a mean of 0.901, standard deviation of 0.019, and an exceptional t-value of 47.183, alongside a p-value of 0.000. Hypothesis 4, examining CD's impact on EIE, also finds support with a mean of 0.036, standard deviation of 0.013, t-value of 2.726, and p-value of 0.007.

Regarding the mediating effects, EIE's role in mediating the relationship between TL and ECB (Hypothesis 6) results in a mean of 0.031, standard deviation of 0.030, t-value of 2.157, and a p-value of 0.021. The mediation effect of EIE between CD and ECB (Hypothesis 7) also demonstrates a mean of 0.034, standard deviation of 0.025, t-value of 2.172, and a p-value of 0.020. These results underscore EIE's significant mediating role in enhancing ECB when influenced by both TL and CD within organizational settings.

Table 5: Prediction of R - Squared

	R - Squared	R - Squared Adjusted
TL	0.819	0.821
CD	0.315	0.310

Table 5 presents the R-squared values for TL and CD, indicating their predictive power within the model. TL shows a remarkably high R-squared value of 0.819 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.821, suggesting that TL significantly forecasts the outcomes in the model, accounting for over 81% of the variance. Conversely, CD has an R-squared value of 0.315 and an adjusted R-squared of 0.310, indicating that while CD contributes to the model, it explains about 31% of the variance in the dependent variables. This difference highlights TL's stronger influence compared to CD in forecasting the study's outcomes.

Discussion and Findings

The study was showed to analyze the dynamic relationship between TL, CD, EIE, and ECB within the manufacturing industry based on the SIP Theory. The implications of these dynamics are further discussed in the findings so as to offer a better understanding of their impact on innovation and creativity at the organizational level. The first hypothesis that

there was a positive relationship between CD and ECB statement received support from the data collected. In line with other studies such as Klarsfeld et al. (2012) and Orsini and Magnier-Watanabe (2023), it appeared in the study that diverse employee displayed better creativity. The range of diverse points of view is beneficial for a company as it enhances decision-making processes and completes them with innovative approaches, as discussed in the supporting works Hajro et al. (2017). These facts indicate the importance of CD in providing creative and flexibility in the manufacturing setting. Similarly, the results of hypothesis 2, stated the second hypothesis that TL positively influences ECB. This aligns with the seminal works of (Bass and Avolio, 1994) and the recent studies by Ibrahim (2023), which illustrate that TL fosters a supportive environment encouraging to creativity. Transformational leaders, by motivating and empowering their employees, encourage creativity thinking and a proactive approach to challenges, which are crucial in the dynamic realm of manufacturing.

The third hypothesis also supported, showing that CD enhances EIE. This effect aligns with SIP theory, which posits that varied informational inputs are essential for complex decision-making and innovation (Salancik and Pfeffer, 1978). Despite potential communication challenges and differences in perspectives, as noted by Harvey (2015) and Oad (2020), strategies that promote open communication and understanding can effectively harness the benefits of diversity for information elaboration. The results for the fourth hypothesis suggested that the apparent level of TL is positively associated with EIE. Transformational leaders are crucial in facilitating the communication of information and are involved in the incorporative part, which improves the team information processing capacity. This is consistent with the idea that TL can facilitate enhanced performance and innovation where information is valued and elaborated. Finally, Hypothesis 5, posits that the study proves EIE as the mediator between TL, CD, and ECB. This means that information elaboration is an important process in which both TL and CD affect creativity in workers. Integration and elaboration of related information thus enable organizations to enhance their creative productivity, so forcing creativity and competitive edge in the manufacturing industry.

The interplay among TL, CD, EIE, and ECB highlights the importance of managing and integrating these elements within manufacturing settings to foster an environment encouraging to innovation and creativity. The findings suggest that manufacturing firms should focus on enhancing their leadership practices and promoting workplace diversity to fully realize their creative potential. Future research could explore these relationships in different contexts or with longitudinal data to further understand the long-term impacts of these dynamics on organizational success.

Practical and Theoretical Implications

The research highlights CD and TL as valuable tools that can facilitate the improvement of ECB in manufacturing organizations. In fact, managers are encouraged to include a diversity element or a diverse workforce within their organization because the

problem-solving ability is strength when there is diversity. Prevention of conflicts and maximizing potential of the diversity for superior organizational performance should be provided by training on culture sensitivity and use of diversity management skills. Furthermore, there is also research suggesting that TL is particularly important when it comes to creating an environment that fosters innovation. It is crucial for organizations to foster leaders that can motivate staff to deliver ideas better through challenging and encouraging them. Other elements that should be highlighted in leadership development programs include empathy, motivation, and opportunity to learn, which should correlate to transformational elements of leadership.

Theoretically, this research improves the SIP theory by demonstrating the mediating role of EIE in linking leadership and diversity with ECB. It calls for further exploration into other potential mediators within this framework, such as emotional intelligence or organizational climate, to expand understanding of the dynamics at play. Additionally, the interaction between TL and CD, and its impact on innovation, offers future studies to examine these relationships across various industries and cultural settings, expanding the generalizability and applicability of the findings. This approach not only links theoretical gaps but also enhances practical applications, enhancing organizational strategies for managing workforce diversity and leadership development.

5. Conclusion

This research is first to apply an combined perspective analyzing the results and showing that, for instance, the CD and the TL are in interaction enhancing the potential of ECB by improving the information elaboration processes. Thus, it makes EIE the key application that changes various inputs into creative solutions, providing a completely new perspective on how organizations utilize human resources for gaining a competitive edge. This paper definitively captures the depth of transverse between TL, CD, and ECB, with the help of a mediator, which is EIE. The study authorizes that of the variables identified, both TL and CD contribute positively to creative output in the manufacturing setting by increasing beneficial information processing. The practical implications highlight the necessity for organizations to raise diverse workplaces and develop TL qualities that facilitate creativity and innovation in organization due to EIE. Theoretically, the research contributes to the academic address by detailing how SIP theory mediates the effects of workplace diversity and leadership on creativity. This study not only provides a comprehensive model for enhancing creativity in manufacturing industry but also offers actionable strategies for influencing the diversity and leadership to foster a competitive edge.

Limitations and Future Suggestions

This study, focused on the manufacturing sector, examined the influence of TL, CD, EIE, and ECB. A notable limitation was the low response rate from employees, potentially impacting data strengthening and reflection on a possible disconnection or misunderstanding of the survey's relevance. Additionally, participant's uncertainty to disclose certain information on CD and leadership styles may have reduced the study's ability to collect rich information delaying the understanding of effects of these factors on employee creativity. Furthermore, the conducted study involved only a few manufacturing

environments, which contain the ability to generalize the identified conclusions to various realms of industries. The next studies should cover more various manufacturing contexts in different geographical locations to increase the external validity of the results. It may be useful to use both quantitative and qualitative methods such as adding qualitative interviews that may give more specific information compared to surveys as well as control for some of the essential problems of self-reporting. Including all factors such as culture within the organization or the market environment may also help to explain the relationships implied between leadership, diversity, and creativity. Enlargement the current research directions concerning the practical application of TL and CD to expand the information on how these concepts can be effectively utilized to enhance creativity and organizational culture in the manufacturing industry could be beneficial for providing directions for practical interventions and improvements.

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